

GIANT ADRENAL MYELOLIPOMA WITH CHOLELITHIASIS: A REAL TROUBLEMAKER OR AN INNOCENT BYSTANDER?

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ABSTRACT Adrenal myelolipomas are uncommon tumors comprising of mature adipose tissue and hemopoietic cells. These tumors are mostly benign, small and asymptomatic. Diagnosis is typically made incidentally on imaging studies done for other reason. Symptomatic disease and large size are common indications for surgical excision. We report a case of giant right-sided adrenal myelolipoma in an elderly lady that was managed with surgical excision. However, because of concurrent chronic cholecystitis, it could not be ascertained whether the tumor was truly symptomatic or not.

KEYWORDS Adrenal myelolipoma, Cholelithiasis, Hemopoietic cell, Giant

Introduction

Myelolipoma is a rare adrenal neoplasm characterized by its benign nature and indolent course. The incidence varies between 0.08% and 0.2% in various autopsy reports [1]. Most of the adrenal myelolipomas remain asymptomatic and are revealed incidentally in the imaging tests done for other indications [2],[3].

Here, we report a case of giant (20x16x12cm) myelolipoma of the right adrenal gland with concurrent cholelithiasis in an elderly female. The patient presented with right upper quadrant abdominal pain and the tumour was detected on preoperative imaging. Simultaneous cholecystectomy and excision of myelolipoma were done with a favourable postoperative course and symptomatic relief. It remained undetermined whether myelolipoma in our case was a real troublemaker or just an innocent bystander.

Case presentation

A 65-year old female presented with pain in the right hypochondrium for two years. The pain was non-radiating, colicky in nature and mild to moderate in intensity. She had no complaints of anorexia, weight loss, fever or altered bowel habit. Per-abdominal examination revealed a non-tender lump in the right lumbar region.

Routine laboratory parameters including haemoglobin, complete blood count, liver function test and serum creatinine levels were within normal limit. Abdominal ultrasound revealed a large hypoechoic mass (20x15x10cm) in the right suprarenal space along with cholelithiasis. A Computed Tomography (CT) scan of the abdomen was performed for evaluation of a tumour, which showed a significant (20x16x10cm), well-defined fatty lesion in the right suprarenal area. The lesion was displacing the right kidney anteriorly and inferiorly and was also abutting the segment VI of the liver. The upper part of a tumour was extending up to the diaphragm and right postero-lateral abdominal wall (Figure 1, 2).

Given an adrenal tumour, the biochemical profile was performed that showed a normal serum adrenocorticotrophic hormone, cortisol and urinary catecholamine level.

Based on physical examination and imaging, a provisional diagnosis of adrenal myelolipoma with cholelithiasis was made. The patient underwent exploratory laparotomy through right subcoastal incision and cholecystectomy was performed first. The retroperitoneum was then approached with mobilization and medial reflection of the right colon. A large, well-

Copyright © 2019 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.giant-adrenal-myelolipoma
First Received: January 04, 2019
Accepted: January 25, 2019
Manuscript Associate Editor: Ivon Ribarova (BG)

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Fig.1. Computed Tomography Abdominal Scan in Coronal reformation shows a large, circumscribed, fatty lesion (arrows) in the right suprarenal space. The tumor is abutting the liver, right crus of the diaphragm and overlying abdominal wall.

Fig.3. Gross appearance of resected right adrenal gland tumour (size 20x15x12 cm).

Fig.2. Axial section CT Scan shows a right adrenal tumour with cholelithiasis (arrow).

Fig.4. Cut surface of adrenal mass shows bright yellow, fat-like tissue with hemorrhagic foci.

Fig.5. Low power microscopy of the adrenal tumour showing compressed adrenal parenchyma at the periphery (arrow) along with mature fat and islands of hematopoietic cells (Hematoxylin and eosin stain x 50).

Fig.6. High power microscopy of the adrenal tumour showing mature adipocytes along with normal trilineage hematopoietic elements [Hematoxylin and eosin stain x 100].

circumscribed tumour was found seated in the right hepatorenal space and extending up to the diaphragm. The tumour was meticulously freed of renal and retroperitoneal attachments and was resected out (Figure 3, 4).

The postoperative course was uneventful, and she was discharged on day six following surgery. Histopathological examination of an adrenal tumour was consistent with myelolipoma and that of the gallbladder with chronic cholecystitis (Figure 5, 6). The patient is doing well and remains symptom-free at a follow-up of 4 months.

Discussion

Gierke first described adrenal myelolipoma in 1905 and in 1929. Oberling termed this entity 'myelolipomatosis' [4],[5]. Earlier, most of these tumours were detected on autopsy or when they produced symptoms. However, with the development of imaging techniques, the majority of the tumours are now discovered incidentally [3]. Adrenal myelolipomas are mostly observed in adults between 50 and 70 years of age and have no sex predilection. A tumour is typically unilateral and seldom exceeds 5 cm in size [3]. It usually arises from the zona fasciculata of the adrenal cortex. The etiopathogenesis is not yet clear. The prevailing accepted hypothesis is that the tumour develops from the metaplasia of reticuloendothelial cells in the adrenal cortical epithelial cells in response to stimuli such as infection, necrosis or sustained endocrine activation. Other researchers have implicated undifferentiated stromal cells located in zona fasciculata to play a role in tumorigenesis [6].

Mostly the tumour remains clinically silent, however, as it enlarges, symptoms such as abdominal discomfort and pain may develop due to mass effect on the surrounding organs. Acute abdominal symptoms may be produced because of complications like haemorrhage, necrosis and spontaneous rupture of a

bulky tumour. The lesion is usually hormonally inert, but an adrenocortical deficiency may be occasionally associated [7],[8]. Our patient had a huge right-sided adrenal myelolipoma with concurrent chronic cholecystitis. Despite its huge size, the tumour was probably quiescent, and the symptoms were chiefly related to cholecystitis.

The differential diagnosis of adrenal myelolipoma comprises of other fat containing adrenal lesions like angiomyolipoma, lipoma, liposarcoma and adrenal carcinoma. Imaging tests, in particular, CT and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are very effective in characterizing the lesion accurately. The predominance of fat (-10 to -90 Hounsfield unit), heterogeneity of lesion and maintained fat planes help to establish the diagnosis and guide the treatment [9]. Endocrine evaluation is warranted when the diagnosis is unclear because of ambiguous radiological or clinical features [10].

Grossly, the myelolipomas are well-circumscribed but rarely encapsulated. The normal glandular tissue is compressed into a thin rim, mainly when a tumour is bulky. Histologically, myelolipomas are composed of adipocytes and hematopoietic elements in variable proportions. Hematopoietic elements include normoblasts, myelocytes, megakaryocytes, and mature leukocytes. Zones of necrosis, haemorrhage and calcium deposition may be seen, particularly in larger tumours [6].

The management of myelolipoma can be either conservative or surgical. The surgical intervention is indisputably indicated for symptomatic lesions. However, there is no clear consensus on the management of asymptomatic tumours. National Institute of Health (NIH) conference recommends surgical resection of tumours >6cm, monitoring for a <4cm and personalized approach for tumours between 4 -6cm [10]. Patients on conservative treatment should be followed-up biannually with CT or MRI scans. Surgery is indicated if a change in tumour size is detected. In our case, though it cannot be ascertained whether a tumour was truly symptomatic or just an incidental finding,

the large tumour size still justifies the surgical excision. As the risk of complications increases with increasing tumour size, the giant myelolipomas (> 10cm) should be managed surgically in fit patients, regardless of symptoms.

For surgical excision, laparoscopy is considered the standard approach. However, open surgery is still indicated for voluminous tumours (>10cm) or when malignancy is suspected [10]. Prognosis of myelolipoma is excellent; recurrence of a tumour or malignant degeneration has not been reported till date [3].

Conclusion

Although adrenal myelolipoma is uncommon, it should be considered in the differential diagnosis of fatty tumours of retroperitoneal origin. Symptoms at presentation, large tumour size (<6cm) and an increase in the tumour volume shown on two consecutive imaging form the basis for surgical intervention. Nonetheless, for safe management, the preoperative radiological characterization of the tumor must be precise.

Conflict of interest

All authors have read and complied with author guidelines and there are no conflicts of interest.

Funding

None

Patient informed consent

Written consent has been obtained from the patient herself.

Ethics committee approval

The report has been prepared in accordance to Ethical (COPE) guidelines.

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